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WIND TURBINE BLADE THERMO- AERODYNAMICS PERFORMANCE EVALUATION AND COMPUTATIONAL FLUID DYNAMIC MODELLING USING STAR CCM+

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Abstract

Power generation is increasingly a pertinent concern in today's rapidly evolving world. One method of generating power involves utilizing wind vanes to capture wind energy from coastal or elevated locations. This study investigated the thermos-aerodynamic performance of wind turbine for optimal blade performance geometry. The study utilized Star CCM+ commercial software to computationally model the airfoil geometry of NACA wind blades. The design profile for this research was tapered and marginally twisted in the span wise direction toward the downstream of the airfoil. This enabled the profile to be simulated at multiple angles of attack, specifically 0, 5, and 10 degrees. The primary boundary conditions for the domain model encompass a velocity input, pressure outlet, ambient temperature, turbulence intensity, and a no-slip condition at the wall. On average, three million meshes were created with fifteen prism layers on the blade's wall. The convergence was guaranteed with blade wall $Y^+ < 1$. The result indicated optimal performance when angle of attack are position between 5 and 10 degrees. Contrary to previously projected operational velocity of 3.45 m/s the blade performed at lower environmental wind velocity of 1.85 m/s. The airfoil exhibits enhanced performance at this angle of attack, accompanied by moderate pressure penalty, noise, and reliability concerns.

Keywords: Airfoil modification, pressure penalties, renewable energy, wind energy, velocity inlet, computational modelling

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1.0 Introduction

Wind energy is the process of converting the energy in moving air into electricity (Abdelgalil *et al.*, 2020). Wind energy is a form of renewable energy because it is generated naturally abundance for possible energy needs by harvesting air energy relative to the surface of the earth (Mehrjerdi, 2020). It is also defined as the process of capturing kinetic energy from wind and converting it into usable mechanical power. Wind energy turbine is categorized into two major types, which are: (1) Horizontal-axis wind turbine (HAWTs) and (2) Vertical-axis Wind turbine (VAWTs). HAWTs typically have three blades, due to optimal performance exhibited and the less aerodynamics loss (Abdelgalil *et al.*, 2020). All the components (including the blades, shaft, and generator) are on top of a tall tower with the blades facing into the wind and the shaft horizontal to the ground. HAWTs are affected by recurrent wind direction changes as compared to the vertical axis wind turbine (Franchina *et al.*, 2020). It is consistent and its rotational speed is high. The shaft is mounted near ground level due to the difficulties of mounting the shaft and its components on the tower. An advantage of being mounted at ground level is that maintenance of the turbine is easier and can be installed at locations such as rooftops. When HAWTs are compared to VAWTs, VAWTs have the disadvantages of low efficiency due to air drag and low wind speed compared to HAWTs. The first signs of humans using wind energy can be dated as far back as 5,000 B.C. when it was used to push boats along

the Nile (Daniel *et al.*, 2022). There is also evidence that buildings were designed to use natural ventilation around the same period. Later, in Babylonia during the 17th century B.C., Emperor Hammurabi made plans to use wind power for an ambitious irrigation project. In the Middle East and Persia, windmills were used to grind grain. In China around 200 B.C., they were used to pump water. This technology progressively made its way to Europe. One of the earliest windmills in the UK can be traced back to 1185 in Weedley, Yorkshire. In China and Italy, windmills were used to pump seawater for salt production. During the 14th century, the Dutch used windmills to undertake the huge project of draining the Rhine delta. In 1887, Professor James Blyth of Anderson's College, Glasgow, Scotland (now Strathclyde University), created the first wind turbine for electricity production, which he used to power the lighting in his holiday cottage. During the 1920s, George Darrieus, a French aeronautical engineer, developed the Darrieus turbine, the first vertical-axis wind turbine, which he got patented in the US in 1931.

Studies have been performed to improve the performance of wind energy and to making it readily available for use both in computational, numerical, and experimental research. According to Mohamed *et al.*, (2015) & Zhang *et al.*, (2020), vertical Axis wind turbine like the Darrieus turbine appear to be promising for the condition of low wind speed and their relatively low efficiency. For global performance of the

wind turbine numerical analysis is introduced to improve the work. The turbine performance with different airfoil shapes can be assessed using computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) procedure. Application of wind turbine is vortex generators which has the capabilities to delay the steady flow, the test for steady and unsteady flow in a wind turbine is caused by a sinusoidal pitching motion, as discussed by Tavernier et al (2021). In a research study by Macphee et al. (2015), for passive adaptation of local wind conditions the blade is built with a flexible material for a low cost. Franchina et al. (2020) researched the three-dimensional unsteady aerodynamics of a H-shaped vertical axis wind turbine over the full operating range. Tavernier et al (2021) carried out a numerical study on controlling dynamic stall using a vortex generator on a wind turbine airfoil. Reza et al. (2022) carried out an analytical design of a radical-flux PM generator for a direct-drive wind turbine renewable energy application.

Hasan, (2020) researched the modelling, integrating, and optimal selection of the turbine technology in the hybrid wind photovoltaic renewable energy. In this journal, optimal plan hybrid wind PV systems are being presented with a novel model. Martinez-Marquez et al. (2022) studied the State-of-the-art review of product stewardship strategies for large composite wind blades. Zidane et al., (2023) studied the effect of upstream used in H-D turbine performance, using the effect of rotor

addition and computational incompressible, transient turbulence model for the vane, the performance was presented before and after the inclusion of the rotor at different deflection vane configurations and it was revealed that single deflector has optimum deflection of 24 % compare to 22 % performance for double deflectors in torque and tip speed ratio. According to Pope et al. (2010) and Nobile et al. (2014) stator vane was also studied to have similar performance. This was further buttressed by Zidane et al., (2020) using CFD-BEM based neural network. Alqurashi and Mohamed (2020) carried out the effect of the rotor vane aerodynamic characteristic effect on system optimisation of H-D turbine. The aerodynamics performance was also studied by Fatehi et al., (2019) and Aboujaoude et al, (2022) using savonius wind turbine axisymmetric nation to simulate the vane performance characteristic. This journal focuses on the integration of material to reduce the environmental impact of wind turbine blade waste. Desalegn et al., (2022) researched a wind energy conversion technology and engineering approaches to enhancing wind power generation. This study is aimed at evaluating the thermo-aerodynamic performance and computational fluid dynamics modeling of a wind turbine blade using CCM+.

2.0 Literature Review

This section discusses the relevant literature in relations to focus of this study. The literature therefore covers the details that define the

framework for the research focus with background understanding of study to indicate the lacuna in the study area.

2.1 Previous studies on computational studies

Mohamed et al., (2015) carried out numerical simulation on CFD analysis for H-rotor

Darrieus turbine as a low-speed wind energy converter, in the study global performance of the wind turbine was improved on this work. Sliding mesh approach, presented in Figure 1, was used to get the speed ration and URANS turbulent calculation. Share stress turbulence (SST), K-omega model is used to improve the accuracy of ANSYS Workbench.

Figure 1: Geometrical feature and main dimensions of the computational domain (Source: Mohamed et al., 2015).

Also, Bhargav et al., (2016) studied the influence of fluctuating wind conditions on vertical axis wind turbine using a three-dimensional CFD model. In this Journal, 3D unsteady analysis is employed to investigate the effect of fluctuating

wind conditions on the performance of a 1.1kW commercially viable VAWT. The effect of fluctuation amplitude is studied by running simulation Figure 2.

Figure 2: (a) 2D view of the domain area (b) 3D view of the meshed domains (Source: Bhargav et al., 2016)

Franchina et al., (2020) carried research on the three dimensional unsteady aerodynamic of a H-shaped VAWTs over full operating range. This journal focuses basically on a study of a H-shaped VAWT over the entire range of

operation. A 2D-3D CFD model was being used for the entire turbine operation curve Figure 3. The study helped to assess the turbine performance and time resolved velocity measurement in the wake.

3: Wind turbine geometry and axis coordinate system (Source: Franchina et al., 2020).

Tavernier et al, (2021) carried out a numerical study on controlling dynamics stall using vortex generator on a wind turbine air foil Figure 4. The effect of Vortex Generators (VGs) in unsteady flow was demonstrated in this study figure 4a. The steady and unsteady flow caused by a sinusoidal pitching motion is being tested in the

wind tunnel and monitored by the actuator control system Figure 4b. For the measurement of the range of cases are lift, drag and moment. They served as validation purposes to assess if the current modelling strategies are in unsteady condition as presented in Figure 4c.

Figure 4: CAD-drawing of the components used in the test set-up (a) Vortex generator strips, (b) Linear actuator © Airfoil model (Source: Tavernier et al., 2021)

MacPhee et al., (2015) carried out the experimental and fluid structures interaction analysis of a morphing wind turbine, the procedural steps for the operation carried out is detailed in Figure 5. In this research, the wind turbine blade was purposefully built of a flexible

material. This made the cost of the design low and simple due to the flexibility of the design. The wind turbine was analyzed using a finite-volume fluid-structure interaction solver. It showed that the flexible rotor was markedly higher to a geometrically identical rigid one.

Figure 5: Overview of FSI algorithm (Source: MacPhee et al., 2015).

Abdelgalil et al., (2020) carried out an experimental and Numerical Investigation on the effect of blade number on the aerodynamic performance of a small-scale horizontal axis wind turbine Figure 6. These focus on the effect of the number of blades on the power and the thrust coefficient of a small HAWT (Horizontal

Axis Wind Turbine). There was a installation on wind turbine rotors with different numbers of blade in the closed circuit open-testsection. It was performed using steady-RANS method. It was known that decrease in the number of blades will make the turbine less sensitive.

Figure 6: Three and five blade wind turbine's rotor configurations (Source: Abdelgalil et al., 2020)

Nelson-Gruel et al., (2020) studied the closed loop control of control of an aerodynamic load fluctuation on wind turbines airfoil using surface plasma actuator Figure 7. By means of active flow control this journal was focused on the alleviation of aerodynamic load fluctuation.

The efficiency of wind turbine loses when it faces a wind gust. Experiment in a wind tunnel and numerical modeling was used to conduct the proofs of concepts. The disturbance rejection test was to assess the control.

Figure 7: Gust angle effect on the lift (Source: Nelson-Gruel et al., 2020).

Hasan Mehrjerdi, (2020) carried research on the modelling, integrating and optimal selection of the turbine technology in the hybrid wind photovoltaic renewable energy. In this journal, optimal plan hybrid wind PV systems are being presented with a novel model. Hybrid wind photovoltaic system have attracted more

attention due to the system cost reduction, improved performance, low emission and noise reduction. Among all, Wind speed has a great impact on the designated turbine technologies when this compound strategies are used Figure 8.

Figure 8: Typical wind turbine curve (Source: Hasan Mehrjerdi., 2020).

Kim et al., (2020) carried out the numerical investigation of the effect of cavity flow on high-speed train pantograph aerodynamic noise, the domain area for the study is presented in Figure 9(a). The grids integrated in the setup was used to refine the surface of the cavity, Figure 9(b). The effect of the pantograph cavity was studied by comparing the flow behavior, radiation and noise from cases with and without

the cavity. When the pantograph was installed in cavity the shear layer, separated from the cavity leading edge, interact with the pantographs and generate large pressure fluctuation on the pantograph surface. The main noise source is from the panhead of the raised pantograph. A slightly lower velocity occurs upstream of the panhead of the raised pantograph for cases with cavity because of the cavity flow.

Figure 9: (a) 3D computational domain, (b) Detail view of leading mesh (Source: Kim et al., (2020))

Zhang et al., (2020) carried research on a numerical study on choosing the best configuration of the black vertical axis wind turbine. In this study the influence of the aero foil maximum camber as well as its position along the chord on the performance of the VAWT were studied Figure 10 presented the computational domain of the study. The

influence of the aero foil thickness is studied based on the two-dimensional symmetrical NACA 4 digits aero foil. The straight black with symmetrical airfoil presented the best power efficiency. Study was further implemented by the efforts of Saad et al., 2021 and Shen et al., (2024) which was experimentally established by these studies.

Figure 10: The computational domain and boundary conditions of the 2-D model (Source: Zhang et al., 2020)

The literature demonstrates the breadth of research conducted in this field. It is noteworthy that, despite existing studies, the impact of functional parameters of turbine blades, as affected by environmental factors such as orientation angle, has not been extensively investigated. The impact of operational flow velocity on climate effects was not addressed. The existing literature focusses on empirical model correlations, utilising various wind speeds across different geopolitical zones in Africa Ajayi et al. (2013); Ajayi et al. (2015). Also, techno-economic implications of insufficient wind energy assessment were examined. The studies

indicate that a significant factor limiting the utilisation of wind energy systems is the site-specific wind vane, which affects the operational efficiency of wind turbines in our regions. The study by Ajayi et al. (2014) indicates that there has been a reduction in the usage of renewable energy, which has adversely affected economic growth and technological advancement across Africa. Baadu and Otoo, (2024) provided an overview of the challenges and benefits of wind energy. In Africa, wind energy is abundant; however, its utilisation is constrained by the inadequate onsite design of wind vanes that effectively capture the available wind energy. Of the estimated 100 GW of

abundant wind power, only 5.7 GW is harnessed, with 90 % of this harvested energy primarily located in Southern and Northern African countries. This comprehensive review identifies policy, competition, and economic factors as major issues, while functional design parameters such as angle of orientation, operational velocity, and pressure generation are not recognised as challenges. This study focusses on this area to provide solutions and enhance design parameters for the system.

3.0 Materials and Methods

Wind Turbine material depends on the make and model which is being built according to a report from the National Renewable Energy Laboratory. The wind turbine material consists of various component which are Steel with about 66-79 % of the turbine mass, Iron or cast iron with about 5-17 %, fiberglass, resin, or plastic with about 11-16 %, copper with 1% and lastly the aluminum with about 0-2 % of the turbine mass. Also, many turbines component are being manufactured in the United States (US). Furthermore, wind turbine tower is 60-75 % sourced, nacelle assemblies are over 85% sourced and blade and hub components are 30-50 % sourced according to the Land-Based Wind Market Report by the office of Energy Efficiency & Renewable Energy (Marquez et al., 2022). Nevertheless, many internal parts are typically imported which are pitch and yaw systems, bearings, bolts, and controllers.

3.1 Operation of Wind Turbine

Wind turbines use blades to collect the kinetic energy of the flowing wind. Wind flows over the blades creating lift like the effect on airplane wings, which causes the blade to turn. The blades are connected to a drive shaft that turns into an electric generator, which generates electricity. Wind electricity generation has grown significantly in the past 30 years. Advances in wind energy technology have decreased the cost of wind electricity generation. To ensure improve wind turbine performance adequate design strategies must be in place. A typical design and operational technique are the application of design and modelling software such as Star CCM+ to design and simulate characteristic behaviour of the profile for specific purpose. To carryout modelling, three main processes are followed; the preprocessing, processing, and post-processing.

Figure 11 presents the detail airfoil novel geometry adapted from NACA 14 airfoil profile and design for preprocessing stage of this study. The preprocessing stage model is generated from SolidWorks™ commercial software, the airfoil profile is designed and save with the Star CCM+ extension file format, Parasolid, the extension enables the Star CCM+ to view on the workbench. The complete wind turbine profile, Figure 11(a) is imported into the Star CCM+ workbench interface processing activity of the simulation on the workbench. Having imported the profile into the workbench, the fluid region

is created and part sectioning are carried out to separate it into sections. The sections are named, sidewall1, figure 11b, sidewall2, figure 11c, Trailing edge wall, Figure 11d, Outlet, figure 11e, Leading edge wall, figure 11f, inlet, figure 11g and finally the profile, figure 11h. The separation of region into parts made adequate

analysis of the setup efficient during post processing activity. After successful model region creation, the mesh is created with vane region domain refined to give accurate result and

Figure 11: Domain wall configuration (a) blade airfoil geometry, (b) Wall 1 Region, (c) Wall 2 Region, (d) Outlet Region (e) Trailing Edge Wall, (f) Leading Edge Wall, (g) Inlet Region, (h) Blade Region

The created mesh is presented in figures 11 (b – h) to show the refine region of the mail vane profile. A total of three (3) million mesh is generated and this was arrived at after mesh integrity validation for pressure drop data. From Table 1, the detail of mesh and boundary conditions for the study are specified. Refined mesh is achieved by adding 10 additional prism layers compared to 5 that are used in all other

regions of the model, also the prism layer stretching of 1.2 are used while others used 1.5 and 20 % prism layer thickness applied to the vane compare to 15 applied to others. These made the vane profile mesh refined to give improve and accurate result in the region while all other regions are set to same condition of mesh as specified above.

Table 1: Mesh and boundary condition

Blade	Mesh	Number of Prism Layers - 15 Prism Layer Stretching - 1.2 Prism Layer Thickness – 20%
	Physics	Tangential Velocity Specification Wall Surface Specification Turbulence Suppression Option Blended Wall Function
Inlet	Mesh	Custom Surface Curvature Custom Surface Proximity Custom Surface Size Customize Prism Mesh
	Physics	Flow Direction Specification Reference Frame Specification Turbulence Specification Velocity Magnitude = 4.0m/s
Outlet	Mesh	Custom Surface Curvature Custom Surface Proximity Custom Surface Size Customize Prism Mesh
	Physics	Pressure Reference Frame Specification Turbulence Intensity
Trailing Edge Wall	Mesh	Custom Surface Curvature Custom Surface Proximity Custom Surface Size Customize Prism Mesh
	Physics	Shear Stress Specification Tangential Velocity Specification Wall Surface Specification Blended Wall Function
Leading Edge Wall	Mesh	Custom Surface Curvature Custom Surface Proximity Custom Surface Size Customize Prism Mesh Customize Surface Remeshing
	Physics	Shear Stress Specification Tangential Velocity Specification Wall Surface Specification Blended Wall Function
Wall 1	Mesh	Custom Surface Curvature Custom Surface Proximity Custom Surface Size Customize Prism Mesh Customize Surface Remeshing
	Physics	Shear Stress Specification Tangential Velocity Specification Wall Surface Specification Blended Wall Function

Wall 2	Mesh	Custom Surface Curvature Custom Surface Proximity Custom Surface Size Customize Prism Mesh Customize Surface Remeshing
	Physics	Shear Stress Specification Tangential Velocity Specification Wall Surface Specification Blended Wall Function

From Table 2 the common material for the wind tunnel applications is presented, the is carried out to give available local material that can be used in the production of wind turbine vane. The steel material could be sourced and produced locally from the foundry. Rotor are prepared in

same manner using steel, fibre, epoxy, and glass. The gear are going to be sourced locally and improvised to obtain the needed ration after design. Finally, the is made of concrete, and steel reinforced bar.

Table 2Materials for wind turbine components

Component	Materials
Tower	Lattice Part: Steel Tubular Part: Steel Transition Piece: Steel Connections: Steel
Rotor	Hub: Cast Iron, glass fiber, epoxy Blades: glass fiber and epoxy (95%), steel (5%)
Nacelle	Gearbox: steel (98%), aluminum (1%), copper (1%) Generator: steel (65%), copper (35%) Frame, Machinery, Shell: Steel (85%), aluminum (9%), copper (4%), glass reinforced plastic (3%)
Foundation	Concrete Steel reinforcement bars

3.2 Governing equations

The governing equations for the motion of a fluid are guided by the a system of partial differential equations derived from conservation laws of continuity equation (mass conservation), the Navier–Stokes equation (momentum conservation), and the general heat transfer equation (energy conservation). These equations are the basis for analysing the fluid dynamics in wide range of its applications from aerodynamics to thermal systems.

3.2.1 Continuity Equation (Mass Conservation)

When a fluid is in motion, it must move in such a way that mass is conserved. To see how mass conversation places restrictions on the velocity field, consider the steady flow of fluid through a duct (that is, the inlet and outlet flows do not vary with time) Aasa et al. (2022) and Tripathi, et al., 2022).

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho u) = 0 \tag{1}$$

Where: ρ is the fluid density, u is the velocity vector, and t is time.

3.2.2 Navier–Stokes equation (Momentum Conservation)

The Navier–Stokes equations mathematically express momentum balance and conservation of mass for Newtonian fluids and also account for inertia, viscous and external forces, Rusli et al., (2025).

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \cdot \nabla u = -\frac{\nabla P}{\rho} + \nu \nabla^2 u \quad 2$$

where u is the fluid velocity vector, P is the fluid pressure, ρ is the fluid density, ν is the kinematic viscosity, and ∇^2 is the Laplacian operator.

3.2.3 General heat transfer equation (Energy Conservation)

The relationship between these quantities is expressed in the heat transfer formula through conduction given by: energy Equation incorporates heat transfer, work done by pressure and viscous forces, and thermal conduction. For a compressible fluid, it is expressed as, Rusli et al., (2025) and Li et al., (2020).

$$\rho \frac{\partial e}{\partial t} + \rho u \nabla e = -p \nabla \cdot u + \nabla \cdot (k \nabla T) + \tau : \nabla u + \dot{Q} \quad 3$$

where e is the specific internal energy, k is the thermal conductivity, T is temperature, and Q represents external heat sources Saini et al., (2020).

$$\dot{Q} = KA(T_1 - T_2) * L \quad 4$$

where Q/t is the rate of heat transfer, k is the thermal conductivity, A is the area, $T_1 - T_2$ is the temperature difference, and L is the thickness.

3.2.4 Data reduction and Analysis

Having simulated the wind profile as specified above in preprocessing, processing the next stage is post processing. The post processing involved the data extraction for the considered parameter(s) which in this case pressure at various considered velocity are extracted to present the overviews of flow behaviours around the vane. Evaluating parameters like pressure, speed, power efficiency, air density, wind turbine power, minimum height of a wind turbine and other relevant values are frequent steps in the data reduction and analysis process. For this case pressure data is obtained at various speed and angle of attacks of operations and. Some studies focus on determining the turbine's parameters at maximum capacity factor, while others consider the maximum density of rated output power Ajayi et al., (2015). These two methods complement each other. If a higher capacity factor is desired, it is important not to choose turbine rated speed too high. This ensures that even though the turbine may operate at rated power for most of the time, it can still get a significant amount of energy from higher-speed winds. Contrarily, if the capacity factor is set too low, although the turbine may generate a higher amount of output power at rated speed, it will rarely operate at its rated power and will miss out on much of the energy

available in lower-speed winds. The evaluation of functional parameters such as speed, pressure, power efficiency, air density, wind power, and height carried out for detailed analysis. The data are extracted using derive part in the Star CCM+ solutions setup. This is based on the solvers and operations user define equation that has made the simulation to process the static pressure of flow for the speed of flow and at the specified angle of attacks, 0°, 5° and 10°.

4.0 Results and Discussions

4.1 Pressure Distribution on the blade

The pressure distribution on the blade wall usually involves the pressure variation from the leading edge to the trailing edge of the vane blade. Static pressure distribution is shown in Figure 2. This revealed the plots for 0-degree AOA (Angle of Attack) the pressure varies from negative pressure to positive pressure for the pressure side and the suction side of the vane. High pressure variations on the pressure side for 0 deg. AOA implies low speed on the blade surface while for 5°. and 10° deg. There is high acceleration on the pressure sides.

Figure 12: Static pressure distribution at the mid span of the blade

From the result in the Figure 12, it shows the graphical representation of the three-plane section that for 0° deg. AOA (Angle of Attack) the pressure varies from negative pressure to positive pressure for the pressure side and the suction side of the vane. High pressure

variations on the pressure side for 0°. AOA implies low speed on the blade surface while for 5°. and 10°. there is high acceleration on the pressure sides.

Figure 13: Static pressure distribution

In Figure 13 averaged pressure is presented at the mid-span for all the AOA investigated. It is observed that the average pressure reduces as a result of the change in AOA. Besides, it can also be observed that the lowest pressure occurs

between 5° < AOA < 10°. The pressure drops from Figure 13 implies rapid acceleration at the downstream of the blade surface. It seems AOA between 5° -10°. Will be sufficient for maximum power output for the wind blade.

Figure 14: Averaged Pressure against AOA

Figure 14 presents static pressure on the entire blade at different AOA. The static pressure deduces towards the tapered and twisted blade surface. In Figure 15 (a), most of the flow that are coming in goes to zero at the leading surface of the blade. This gives rise to high pressure as shown in Figure 4 at the leading surface of the blade. However, in Figure15, a very high wake is observed to have developed downstream of the blade. This seems to cause a reduction in the movement of the blade about its axis. As the

blade tapers off in Figure14, there is a gradual reduction in the blade. From Figure 6a, the magnitude of the static pressure is very high, creating very high flow separation at the downstream part of the blade. This high flow separation seems to disperse just in Figures 15 (b) and (c), just about 1 axial chord downstream of the blade profile. Figures 15 (a) and 16 (a) show a proportional trend, while Figures 16 (b) and (c).

Figure 15: Static Pressure on the blade surface (a) 0° AOA (b) 5° AOA (c) 10° AOA

Figure 16: flow Velocity along the x-axis [i-direction] on the blade surface at the mid-span
(a) 0° AOA (b) 5° AOA (c) 10°

5.0 Conclusion

This study examines the thermo-aerodynamic aspects of wind energy performance in the region, highlighting the key findings derived from the research. It is noteworthy that the angle of attack (AOA) influences the pressure and flow separation occurring during operation, as indicated by this computational fluid dynamics (CFD) analysis. The influence of angle of attack (AOA) is evident in the significant pressure drop observed, with 0° AOA exhibiting the highest pressure drop, while 5° and 10° AOA show minimal pressure variation. At varying AOAs, a greater pressure drop is recorded at the leading edge in comparison to the trailing edge, with 0° AOA again demonstrating the most substantial pressure drop. A uniform pressure distribution is more evident at 10° angle of attack compared to 5° and

0° angle of attack. This observation is based on the flow separation occurring at the trailing edge of the profile. Overall performance of the profile shows that 0° AOA as the lowest performance and 10° AOA as the best performance. This is observed as the pressure drop as AOA increases.

Author's Contribution Statement

Regan K. Dunne, specialises in writing review and editing, supervision, funding acquisition, formal analysis.

Dawood A. Desai, specialises in writing review and editing, supervision, formal analysis.

Samson A. Aasa specialises in writing, including review and editing, original drafts, validation, project administration, investigations, formal analysis, and conceptualisation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

We declare that this study has no competing of interest be it financial or personal interest that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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